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A CNN-LSTM Model for Intrusion Detection System from High Dimensional Data

Dr K Praanna¹, SVP Sruthi², K V Kalyani³, A Sai Tejaswi⁴

¹Associate Professor, AITS, Rajampet, ^{2,3,4}AITS, Rajampet

¹prasanna.k642@gmail.com, ²prasanna7185514@gmail.com, ³kalyanikusireddy@gmail.com,

⁴saitejeswialam999@gmail.com

Abstract

Network protection is an essential part of attack detection. Machine learning algorithms play an important role in the current Intrusion Detection. However, these algorithms are suffering with low accuracy and detection rate. Deep learning is another sophisticated technique to solve these challenges because intrusion detection performance is not strong in traditional machine learning systems. This article examines network intrusion detection using a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and LSTM. The integrated folding and grouping operations are used to derive the relationship of the features between the results. The model should automatically determine the efficient properties of the intrusion samples so that the intrusion samples can be classified accurately. Experimental tests with KDD99 data sets suggest that the proposed model will significantly increase intrusion detection performance.

Keywords: Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), LSTM, Intrusion Detection System, Accuracy, KDD99, Machine Learning

1. Introduction

The Internet, along with business networks, plays an important role in global economic and commercial development. As network technology evolves, physical devices are linked to the Internet. Communication between devices resulted in the generation and storage of a large amount of data in the form of high dimensional data. However, the variety of network attacks and their continually changing nature can make it difficult to achieve a secure network. Flexible defense methods are needed that can quickly investigate large amounts of network traffic and accurately detect different types of attacks [18].

In network security, anomaly-based intrusion detection systems are valuable methodologies for identifying known and unknown or new attacks. Anomaly-based IDSs are trained to continually observe normal patterns of behavior and recognize any deviations or abnormalities from existing normal behaviors [2]. In anomaly-based intrusion detection systems, the occurrence of an anomaly can provide critical information. For example, an unusual network traffic pattern could mean that a server is under attack and that data is being moved to an unapproved destination. Anomalies in network traffic highlight not only previously known attacks, but also identify entirely new attack patterns. However, in many scenarios, the abnormalities can be normal behaviors that have simply not yet been identified. Therefore, anomaly-based network intrusion detection systems must continually update with new behaviors and new network protocols.

In recent years, a class of machine learning algorithm, called deep learning, has been increasingly used in classification and pattern recognition. Deep learning applies

multiple layers of information processing in a hierarchical architecture to generate a deep model [24] [5] [27]. In the field of intrusion detection, a limited number of research studies have investigated deep learning, but none of them have efficiently exploited the full power of deep learning techniques [2][12]. AlphaGo [3], an innovative deep learning software program, uses CNN to test a policy network. CNN-based ResNet and GoogleNet malware identification frameworks are studied in [15], [16]. CNN platform for pattern recognition focused on identifying malicious applications are used in [17]. Furthermore, although CNNs have been recognized as highly accurate, they have not been exploited in the IDS field [3]. Network networks can become increasingly fragile as the number of networked devices increases. It helps hackers to access information more quickly [7]. While people have done everything possible to secure sensitive details, cyber attacks tend to occur [25]. This is where we believe CNN can make a difference. In this document, we try to use CNN to address the low accuracy and high false alarm rates in conventional IDS.

This article studies the identification of network interference based on Convolutional neural networks (CNN), LSTM and integrates Convolution and grouping operations to help extract the function relationship between the results. This not only struggles to address the problem in conventional machine learning models. The remaining paper is organized as follows. Section 2 will describe about related research work. Section 3 will present more detailed description about the proposed CNN-LSTM integration along with maxpooling for efficiently discovering Intrusion Detection System. The performance analysis is presented in section 4 followed by Conclusion in section 5.

2. Related Research Work

This segment would debate the theoretical work carried out at IDS. A series of algorithms for IDS are built in the literature. An essential aspect of protecting the computer network is intrusion prevention technology. In 1980 the idea of intrusion detection was first suggested [8]. The goal of detecting attacks is to accurately recognize suspicious activity on the network. The most common intrusion prevention approach is to use various machine learning methods to reduce the error rate. A series of human intrusion detection models integrating various machine learning algorithms are developed [19].

A hybrid machine learning algorithm based on SVM that incorporates Zhi-Mean [26] to identify assaults was suggested in [4] to measure and modify the parameters for the similarities between the results. [1] Suggested machine learning methods for network analysis of Zeus V1.x, Zeus V2.x and harmless HTTP traffic. [20], and [6], they have used a Neural network to predict network interference. [28] Suggested the LSSVM network intrusion prevention software. [21], they used secret Markov models to test network interference identification. [20] [22], they used KSVC to identify network intrusions.

Traditional machine learning techniques are very successful in detecting interference, but have drawbacks, since the conventional machine learning system has to create sample characteristics artificially. Their success depends on their consistency. Researchers have implemented deep learning techniques to solve this problem. [13] Implemented deep network trust in intrusion identification and performed better than many conventional machine learning approaches. [11] [23] In the field of intrusion detection, a limited number of research studies have investigated deep learning, but none of them have efficiently exploited the full power of deep learning techniques [18]. Among the different approaches to deep learning, the Convolutional Neural network (CNN) performed significantly in computer vision, such as faces and object recognition.

2.1. Deep Learning:

Deep learning has recently gained a lot of interest and popularity in many fields of research. In our research, we applied one of the well-known deep learning networks called the Convolution Neural Network (CNN) to the IDS to exploit the advantages of functional learning and classification. The basic component of the Neural network is a neuron with an activation mechanism (π), a set of weights (W) and a set of biases (B) [15]. Regarding these parameters, the transformation is defined by:

$$a = \sigma(wTx + b) \quad (1)$$

Where x is the input of the neuron, w is the weight, b is the bias, T is the transposition matrix and σ is the activation function. The Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) is one of the most common neural networks. MLPs have many layers of transformation. MLP has an input layer and an output layer, and can have additional layers that are called secret layers between the input and output layers. In general, a neural network with many hidden layers is considered a deep Neural network [20].

One of the central concepts of deep learning is the calculation of empirical evidence of higher-level characteristics than lower-level characteristics. [6] Recently, CNN has been successfully applied in many jobs, such as image classification, scene text recognition, object tracking, voice recognition, posture estimation, natural language processing, and detection of visual relevance and recognition of human action [6].

2.2. Convolutional Neural Networks:

CNN is a variant of a neural network, whose objective is to learn the correct representations of the characteristics of the input data. There are two main distinctions between a CNN and an MLP: weight distribution and grouping. Each CNN layer can be made up of several Convolution nuclei that are used to create various feature maps. Each adjacent neuron area is linked to a next layer function map neuron. Furthermore, all the spatial positions of the inputs share the nucleus to create the function diagram. For multiple Convolution and grouping layers, one or more complete bound layers are used for classification. Due to the use of mutual weights on CNN, the model can learn the same pattern that appears at a specific entry location without the need for separate detectors for each location to train. And the layout can be stable for input translation [20]. Clustering layers increase computing stress as the number of links between Convolutional layers decreases [6].

A set of n cores $W = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n\}$ and their biases $B = \{b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n\}$ are translated into input data at each CNN layer. A new x_k function map is generated by the Convolution between the data and each core. The transformation is described by: for each Convolutional layer l ;

$$x_k^l = \sigma(w_k^{l-1} * x^{l-1} + b_k^{l-1}) \quad (2)$$

A narrow window moves over the inputs throughout the CNN learning phase, and the bias and weight values through this window can be adjusted from various input data characteristics without their place within the input data [15].

3. CNN-LSTM Model for IDS:

We are examining powerful IDSs from high-dimensional data in this part. A Network Intrusion Detection System (NIDS) is essential for network protection, as it helps you identify and react to malicious traffic. The main objective of an intrusion detection program is to ensure that IT personnel are informed at any time that an assault or network intrusion may occur.

The Convolutional layers transform the input into a Convolution Neural network and transfer the output to the next line. Fully linked feed forward neural networks can be used to learn characteristics and to identify data; extending this model to photos is not

realistic. Given the very large input sizes associated with photos, where each pixel is a specific vector, a large number of neurons will be needed, also in a shallow architecture. This network often includes different steps, i.e. Convolution, maximum grouping, and flattening, down to practice.

- **Convolution layer:** the characteristics are derived from the data.
- **Grouping:** reduces the dimensionality of each feature map but retains the most important information
- **Flatten:** Flatten is converting the data into a one-dimensional matrix to enter it in the next layer. We flatten the output of the Convolutional layers to create a single long feature vector.
- **Fully Connected:** Fully connected layers connect each neuron in one layer with each neuron in another layer.

3.1. LSTM (Long Short Term Memory):

Short-term wide memory (LSTM) is a model of artificial recurrent neural network (RNN) that is used in deep learning. LSTM has input links, unlike normal advancing neural networks. It can process not only individual data points (such as images), but also entire data streams. LSTM, for example, refers to activities such as non-segmented handwriting recognition, voice recognition and the identification of irregularities in network traffic or Intrusion Detection Systems.

A typical LSTM unit consists of a cell, an entry door, an exit door, and a forgetting door. The cell holds values for unpredictable periods of time, and the three doors govern the flows of knowledge inside and outside the cell. LSTM networks are well suited for classifying, analyzing, and forecasting based on time series data, because there may be delays of uncertain length in a time series between significant events. LSTMs have been developed to address the breakdown and disappearance gradient problems that can be found in conventional RNN preparation. Gap length insensitivity is a benefit of LSTM over RNN, hidden Markov models, and other sequence learning approaches in many applications.

3.2. Proposed Architecture of CNN-LSTM Model

CNN based on [7] are deep learning feature extraction models that have recently been shown to be quite effective in image recognition [6], [3], [12], [8]. As of today, numerous business giants like Google, Twitter, and Amazon are using the templates. And recently, Google researchers applied CNN to video data [11]. It is achieved by performing separate transformations of the filter values as trainable weights in the image. Several filters are added to each path, and they form feature maps along with Neural activation functions. A grouping scheme accompanies this, where only the relevant details of the function maps are grouped.

Figure 1: CNN model for Intrusion Detection System

The design of the Convolutional Neural network, as seen in Figure 1, is composed of input, Convolution layer, clustered layer, fully connected layer, and output layer. The CNN networks have diverse architectures with a specific number of levels of Convolution and grouping. The function map of layer i can be represented as the Convolution method: $M_i = f(M_{i-1} \otimes W_i + b_i)$. W_i is the weight vector of the transfer core of layer i , the process representation describes the transfer phase and is the displacement variable of layer i , and (z) is the excitation function. The Convolution nucleus creates new characteristics in the Convolution cycle by performing the Convolution procedure with the characteristics of the inputs.

The concept of "parameter sharing" is observed when confused with a Convolutional nucleus. The number of parameters in the entire neural network is significantly decreases by having the same weights and displacements

Figure 2: Proposed Model for Intrusion Detection

The grouping layer generally samples the function map after the Convolution layer, according to the specific sampling laws. Suppose M for the grouping layer input, H_i is the grouping layer output, then the grouping layer can be represented as $H_i = \text{SubSampling}(M_i - 1)$.

3.3. Intrusion Detection Model Framework

Figure 2 is a paradigm for detecting intrusion attacks centered on the Convolutional Neural Network algorithm with the LSTM-70 as output. Throughout Figure 2, it can be shown that the structure mainly consists of three phases:

- Phase 1: Data preprocessing: The KDD-99 data set has a large amount of unnecessary data preprocessing that allows you to clean up messy data and transform conceptual data into numerical data.
- Phases 2: Training and extraction of characteristics: the constructed CNN model is used for the preparation and extraction of characteristics data.
- Phases 3: Continue. Test: The softmax classifier was used to identify and collect the effects of the test.

To get detailed evidence, we built a Neural Convolution network. The entire network is made up of three hidden layers. The Convolutional layer and a grouping layer are converged as the first 2 layers which comprises as hidden layers. The third layer is an output LSTM layer. With each hidden layer, the number of Convolutions is different. The network uses Convolution cores and shared cores to increase efficiency by constantly expanding the network configuration. The number of conversions should improve accuracy. We build 2 Convolution layers one with 64 filters and 128 filters on the other.

4. Experiments and Analysis

In this section we will revise the performance CNN-LSTM algorithm with SVM, DBN, CNN*. The Accuracy is measured with and compared with SVM, DBN and CNN*. CNN-LSTM an enumeration based hybrid approach algorithm has shown its better performance on Intrusion Discovery system.

4.1. Dataset

In our performance study we used the variant size 10% of the KDD99. The data set contains 5 types of intrusions as shown in table 1. Each intrusion is classified based on its features. We train the model based on this 10% of KDD99 dataset. This data set is partitioned as train and test data. The allocation of different types of intrusions is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Allocation of KDD99 Datasets

Attack Types	Training Examples	Testing Examples
Normal	97277	60592
Denial of Service	391458	237594
Remote to User	1126	8606
User to Root	52	70
Probing	4107	4166
Total Examples	494020	311028

4.2. Data Pre-processing

The dataset used contains attributes per record. It contains 41 features in which 38 are numerical and 3 are symbolic. So dataset need to be preprocessed separately. Heuristic based feature attribute selection was presented in [9], [10].

- Numerical characterization of symbolic features: We created and used a function `encode_text_dummy` for the three symbolic features, if we have red, blue, green, and we converted the 1Dimensional vector into a 3Dimensional vector.
- 2) Normalization of numerical features: There are various measurements for numerical details with numerical features; the scale of numerical element differs. Therefore, to reduce the effect of dimensional variations, numerical measurements must be performed [14].

4.3. Experimental Evaluation

In this experiment we calculated True Positives (TP) and True Negatives (TN) to calculate the Accuracy as:

$$AC = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \quad (3)$$

Among such, TP is properly classified number of attack behaviors; TN is properly classified number of usual behaviors; FP is misclassified number of usual behaviors; FN is misclassified number of attack behaviors.

4.4. Analysis of Experimental Results

The Accuracy of the proposed CNN-LSTM model is measured by setting the Convolution matrix size to 2, convolution duration is set with the duration of the pooling layer by using max pooling. Using the Adam optimization algorithm over convolution matrix the pooling algorithm performs the subsampling to minimize the error function.

We observed improvements in accuracy in the Convolution Neural Network by setting LSTM for output layer.

Table2: Comparison of SVM, DBN, CNN* and CNN-LSTM

Model	Accuracy %
SVM	98.20
DBN	98.59
CNN*	99.23
CNN-LSTM	99.78

Table 2 contrasts SVM, DBN, CNN* and CNN-LSTM algorithms to the identification effect by precision. We can see that the CNN-LSTM model's detection impact is stronger than that of other algorithms. Figure 4 provides a summary of the efficiency of algorithms SVM, DBN, CNN* and CNN-LSTM. It is ascertained from figure 3 that CNN-LSTM has achieved better accuracy performance.

5. Conclusion

Applying the Convolution Neural Network algorithm to intrusion detection is an old concept that gives good accuracy but we tried to combine LSTM with CNN to get more accuracy and render machine more effective. This paper suggests a system by which Convolution Neural Network algorithm and LSTM algorithm are merged. The experimental findings indicate that this model will increase the precision of detection of human interference and boost the efficiency of the detection method for human invasion. It is also pragmatic that the projected representation outperformed with SVM, DBN, and CNN* with CNN-LSTM model.

Figure 3: Comparison of CNN-LSTM and other models

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